

On the Convergence Rate of Nested Square Root Expressions

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Abstract

In this note, we give an explicit upper bound for the difference between an infinite nested square root expression and its finite truncations. Using elementary inequalities, we obtain a quantitative error estimate which guarantees how many nested radicals are sufficient to achieve a desired accuracy.

Main Result

Let $(a_n)_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence of positive real numbers such that the infinite nested radical

$$\sqrt{a_1 + \sqrt{a_2 + \sqrt{a_3 + \cdots}}}$$

is convergent. Define

$$\Delta_n = \sqrt{a_1 + \sqrt{a_2 + \cdots}} - \sqrt{a_1 + \sqrt{a_2 + \cdots + \sqrt{a_n}}}.$$

Clearly, $\Delta_n > 0$.

Multiplying by the conjugate and iterating the same procedure in the numerator, we obtain

$$\Delta_n = \frac{\sqrt{a_{n+1} + \cdots}}{\prod_{k=1}^n \left(\sqrt{a_k + \cdots} + \sqrt{a_k + \cdots + \sqrt{a_n}} \right)}.$$

Using the inequalities

$$\sqrt{a_k + \cdots} \geq \sqrt{a_k}, \quad \sqrt{a_k + \cdots + \sqrt{a_n}} \geq \sqrt{a_k},$$

we get

$$\prod_{k=1}^n \left(\sqrt{a_k + \cdots} + \sqrt{a_k + \cdots + \sqrt{a_n}} \right) \geq \prod_{k=1}^n 2\sqrt{a_k} = 2^n \sqrt{a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n}.$$

Hence,

$$0 < \Delta_n \leq \frac{\sqrt{a_{n+1} + \cdots}}{2^n \sqrt{a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n}}.$$

Explicit Upper Bound

Assume there exists $\lambda > 0$ such that

$$a_{n+k} \leq \lambda^{2^k} \quad \text{for all } k \geq 1.$$

Then

$$\sqrt{a_{n+1} + \cdots} \leq \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \sqrt{\lambda^4 + \sqrt{\lambda^8 + \cdots}}} = \lambda \sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 + \cdots}}}.$$

Let

$$x = \sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 + \cdots}}}.$$

Then $x^2 = 1 + x$, and hence

$$x = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

Therefore,

$$\Delta_n \leq \mu := \frac{\lambda(1 + \sqrt{5})}{2^{n+1} \sqrt{a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n}}.$$

Numerical Guarantee

For a prescribed error tolerance $\mu > 0$, the inequality

$$0 < \sqrt{a_1 + \sqrt{a_2 + \cdots}} - \sqrt{a_1 + \sqrt{a_2 + \cdots + \sqrt{a_n}}} < \mu$$

is satisfied whenever

$$2^{n+1} \sqrt{a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n} \geq \frac{\lambda(1 + \sqrt{5})}{\mu}.$$

Solving this inequality for real n and rounding up to the nearest integer guarantees that the finite nested radical approximation is accurate within the prescribed tolerance μ .